

Twin on a chip brains for monitoring individual sleep habits

Document Title	COD strategy updated
Document Reference	D7.4
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Version	1.0
Report availability	PUBLIC
Date	February 26th, 2025

This document -prepared within the COD strategy and Innovation Potential Work package (WP7) - updates the communication, outreach and dissemination (COD) strategy and the activities that will be carried out during the project to steer the engagement of the different stakeholders - already identified in D7.1.

The whole Consortium is aware that a consistent COD strategy is crucial for showcasing the results, outcomes and impact of the objectives and goals we would like to pursue within NAP. As such, this deliverable is organized in five main sections: after a brief introduction of the main structure of the deliverable, we will define Communication, Outreach and Dissemination. Then, we will detail the COD objectives, in particular focusing on stakeholders, main key messages, tools and timing guiding the development of our activities and actions. Indicators for monitoring the COD plan will be presented. Examples of actions that have already taken place (or are currently underway) are presented, thus giving the reader an indication of their characteristics.

This is the updated version of the COD plan deliverable submitted at M6 (D7.2).

History of changes

Version	Date	Organization	Description/comments
1.0	Feb 18th, 2025	STU	COD strategy updated, taking into account the HOP-ON integrations.
1.1	Feb 25th, 2025	UNIFI	Update of the impact indicators and of the actions already taken

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Introduction

This COD Plan deliverable updates the NAP Communication, Outreach and Dissemination strategy, defined in deliverable D7.2, and both referring to task T7.1 (Dissemination strategies) and T7.2 (Communication and outreach strategy) of Work-Package (WP) 7 (COD Strategy and Innovation Potential). In further describing the project identity, it complements the Deliverable 7.1 “Website and Project Logo”.

In general, our Communication, Outreach and Dissemination objectives are to: i) share NAP methodology and data with the scientific community, ii) show off the NAP envisioned technology potential, iii) raise awareness about the consequences of sleep deprivation and the importance of early-stage diagnosis of neurodegeneration and iv) invite audience engagement and participation.

The objectives of the COD plan are:

- ensure an effective communication, outreach and dissemination of the project
- plan communication, outreach and dissemination activities of the project
- define the criteria for monitoring the effectiveness of the plan
- provide all the Consortium a harmonized strategy to guarantee the success of the described plan.

This document will describe the general strategy, the tools and the indicators that will be adopted to increase the impact of NAP. It will be updated as the project moves on – at M24 - according to the Grant Agreement, so as to take any new needs into account any new necessities and after the constant monitoring of the indicators.

Definitions

Communication, Outreach and Dissemination are central to HORIZON projects, together with exploitation. Each of them is characterized by specific objectives, focus and target stakeholders. The differences are listed below:

- **Communication** aims at reaching out to lay audience and media, in particular showing the impact and the benefits of the project objective and outcomes. It usually goes in one direction (i.e., from the sender to the receiver). The focus is to inform and promote the project and its results with a clear and attractive message able to catch the attention.
- **Outreach** aims at engaging a large audience to inform the general public. Since it implies an interaction between the sender and the receiver of the message, it takes the form of school presentations, workshops, public talks, lab visits, etc.
- **Dissemination** aims at maximizing the impact of the project results, in particular for their re-use. Thus, it is addressed to an audience that potentially can use such results, and it is mainly achieved through scientific papers, public databases, workshops, conference presentations and posters etc.
- **Exploitation** aims at valorizing the project results and knowledge transfer, in particular focusing on commercialization and market aspects (more in D7.3).

Different strategies will be dedicated to Communication, Outreach and Dissemination respectively. Here we will focus on Communication, Outreach and Dissemination, while a detailed presentation of the Exploitation plan will be provided in D7.3.

The COD Plan: Why, who, what, how, when

The COD strategy addresses the following elements:

- Why: COD tailored objectives
- Who: the stakeholders
- What: the tailored key messages
- How: the methods and the tools adopted
- When: Time

Why: COD tailored objectives

The overall objective of the NAP project is to develop a novel science-to-technology paradigm to assess the ability of the next generation of biohybrid *in vitro* brains to serve as downscaled and personalized models of sleep, and to predict sleep-related early signs of Parkinson's Disease. In particular, specific objectives are:

- Design of a protocol for modelling individual sleep/wake habits & sleep loss *in vitro*
- Realization of the *cyborganoids*, the next generation of biohybrid *in vitro* brain models
- Identification of markers of neuronal activity *in vitro* and *in vivo* during sleep and wake
- Extraction of quantitative descriptors of neuron morphology
- Assessment of the degree of similarity of *in vitro* and human data
- Detection of sex-related differences between i) normal sleep/wake & sleep loss, ii) healthy & Parkinson's Disease.

Such objectives can be of potential interest to different stakeholders, from the research community up to investors interested in *cyborganoids* commercialization and patient associations and lay audience interested in learning the importance of sleep, in everyday life and for brain health. Thus, starting from the NAP objectives, specific Communication, Outreach and Dissemination objectives were outlined.

Communication objectives:

- Increase local, national and international visibility of NAP as an EU-funded project
- Present the NAP project's aim to stakeholders, in particular to press and general public
- Raise awareness on the potential of NAP expected outcomes regarding brain health and sleep research
- Increase trust in science and technology, in particular concerning organoids and stem cells for neuroscience
- Make use of visual narratives to guarantee attractive and effective communication

Outreach objectives:

- Increase local, national and international visibility of NAP as an EU-funded project
- Present the NAP project's aim to stakeholders
- Involve and train inspired young students, also including NAP activities as part of academic lessons
- Involve young female students and researchers to strengthen gender equality in research and innovation
- Raise awareness on the potential of NAP expected outcomes about brain health and sleep research
- Increase trust in science and technology, in particular concerning organoids and stem cells for neuroscience

Dissemination objectives:

- Maximize the impact of the project results, delivering open access publication and attending scientific conferences and events relevant for sleep and neuroscience research
- Raise awareness on the potential of NAP expected outcomes regarding brain health and sleep research
- Network with researchers and stakeholders interested in NAP outcomes and innovation potential

To ensure the uptake and maximization of such messages, ideas and the subsequent research results, we will identify appropriate communication, outreach and dissemination strategies for dialoguing with the relevant stakeholders which can potentially benefit of them.

Who and what: the stakeholders and the tailored key messages

Prerequisite of an effective COD strategy is the definition of the target audience and their specific key messages and COD actions.

We have already identified potential stakeholders, as described in the Grant Agreement and in D7.1 “Website and project logo” and as reported in Table 1. For the intrinsic nature of the NAP project, the main potential target groups are very heterogeneous. Based on their characteristics, needs/priorities, we identified tailored key messages and defined modes to approach them.

Table 1 NAP target group & key messages and modes for Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication, Outreach

NAP stakeholders	Target key messages	D	E	C	O
Scientific Community and Organizations	NAP breakthroughs and, in turn, NAP Proof of Principle can give a key contribution to study individual sleep pathophysiology NAP strategy can be customized for quantitatively evaluating the (patho)physiological relevance of different in vitro constructs NAP envisioned technology will identify early-stage PD patients that could be interested in adhering as volunteers to test new therapies	✓	✓		✓
Healthcare operators	The NAP envisioned technology has the potential to predate PD diagnosis, thus decreasing the healthcare costs and simplifying aged care.		✓	✓	
Investors, other financial actors	NAP envisioned technology for predating PD can create real economic value, generating new business in our aging society		✓		
Biotech/Pharmaceutical Industry	The innovation potential of the NAP Proof of Principle and envisioned technology can provide a new tool for drug testing and neurotoxicity	✓	✓		

Citizen groups (e.g., Night workers, Schools, Patients associations)	NAP Proof of Principle and breakthroughs give tangible evidence of the effects of sleep deprivation and disorders on individual brains, raising awareness on the role of prevention and of the early detection of neuropathies. NAP envisioned technology will give the opportunity to routinely screen ourselves and our relatives for predated PD diagnosis			✓	
Space Agencies	NAP envisioned technology will give the opportunity to routinely screen astronauts' sleep and study sleep/wake cycles in weightless environment	✓	✓		
Clinicians	The NAP envisioned technology has an important clinical potential, e.g., as a support for early ND diagnosis	✓	✓	✓	
Policy Makers, Public Authorities	Foster discussion and debate about the potential positive effects of NAP on economy and society, and about the need to strength the e-health and the need to identify new protocols for its managing.		✓	✓	
Journalists	NAP project has a strong scientific, technological and social component on hot topics such as sleep and PD, which attract the public opinion			✓	
General Audience	NAP Proof of Principle funded by EU improve citizen lives since it gives tangible insights on the effects of sleep deprivation and disorders			✓	✓

How: the methods and the tools adopted

UNIPi will coordinate the Communication, Outreach and Dissemination activities, closely working with all the project partners.

'Brand guidelines' were shared among the partners, as a set of elements and guidelines that should characterize the institutional communication of the project, to simplify and make recognizable our communication and dissemination activities.

Given the particular nature of the project, we feel it is important to pay particular attention to our communications, to both specialized and lay audience. Indeed, since NAP aims at developing technologies and knowledge that can be technically complex and challenging, the language we use to communicate might be critical. The same messages, when targeted to different audiences, often need to be expressed in different ways: the language thus needs to become more or less technical according to the different audience. This is particularly true for sensitive arguments, such as pluripotent stem cells and their use to study an intimate habit such as sleep in an individualized manner.

A process is set up to disseminate project messages via the tools and the channels of all partners. This process entails a proactive communication with all the partners when there are events to be disseminated/outreached/communicated. A non-exhaustive list of events that the partners are attending or involved in was already provided in the description of action of the Grant Agreement. All the events will be promptly sponsored on NAP social media accounts

and website. In the shared folder of the consortium, an excel sheet was created, where all partners can update their own COD activities related to the project.

As regards the tools exploited, most of them have been already identified in the Description of Action, for Communication, Outreach and Dissemination, and tailored for the different target groups, as shown in Table 2 and Table 3.

It is worth mentioning that during the second period of the project we decided to prioritize LinkedIn, Instagram and Facebook over X (formerly Twitter).

Table 2 Communication and Outreach tools and the dedicated target groups

Communication and Outreach tools	Target groups
NAP website & social (LinkedIn, Instagram, Facebook, YouTube)	Scientific community & Organizations, Clinicians, Investors, Citizen Groups, Journalists, General Audience (spec Young), Space agencies
Radio, journals and TV	Citizen Groups, Journalists, General Audience
Press kits	Journalists
Newsletters Sleep pills; articles on webzines; blogs; podcasts	General Audience (spec Young); Citizen Groups, Clinicians
Lab visits, Open Doors	General Audience (School), Journalists, Citizen Groups, Pharma/Biotech companies, Investors
Café Science; Research Nights; Sleep & Brain Week	General Audience, Journalists, Citizen Groups
Citizen Science experiment: Let's take a NAP...for NAP	General Audience, Citizen Groups

Table 3 Dissemination tools and the dedicated target groups

Dissemination tools	Target groups
Open Deliverables	Scientific community and organizations, Biotech/Pharma Companies, Space agencies
Open Science publications	Scientific community and organizations, Biotech/Pharma Companies, Space agencies
Conferences & events promoted by Scientific Organizations	Scientific community and Organizations, Biotech/Pharma Companies
Brochure, posters, roll-up banners	Scientific community and Organizations, Citizen Groups, General Audience
Webinars and Demos	Scientific community and Organizations, Biotech/Pharma Companies, Clinicians, Space agencies, Investors
Policy briefs	Policy Makers, Public Authorities

All partners are encouraged to author papers in international journals, as well as in conference proceedings. To this end, many NAP deliverables will be conceived as manuscripts for research papers, so as to optimise the time and effort spent doing research. All research

papers generated by NAP bear the official acknowledgement of EC funding, specifying the Grant Agreement number.

Some of the tools mentioned above have already been created as Communication and Dissemination materials. This material, together with the information already provided in D7.1 “Website and project logo”, where also the social media accounts are detailed, constitutes the visual identity of the project. It has been already shared as a ‘visual identity package’, provided in the OneDrive folder shared among the partners.

For the purpose of the obligations stated in the Grant Agreement, all products will display the EU emblem and include the following text “This project has received funding from the European Union’s HORIZON EIC programme under grant agreement No 101099310”.

The Communication, Outreach and Dissemination materials are briefly described below.

The report, presentation and newsletter templates have already been presented in D7.2 and no changes have been made. On the other hand, the brochure and the roll ups have been updated to include the new partner (STU).

Brochure

The brochure explains the above-mentioned points through images and short sentences, to make it as much communicative as possible, and also comprehensible and attractive for non-experts. Since NAP consortium recently welcome onboard STU as a partner, a new project brochure was elaborated.

A screenshot of the NAP brochure is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 NAP brochure

Roll-up banner

The project roll-up is an easy and important tool to further define the visual identity of the project and properly capture audience attention. The roll-up will be especially used during workshops and events. A screenshot of the new NAP roll-up banner, including the new partner STU, is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 NAP roll-up banner

Press kit

An updated version of the press kit has been made available for reporters, journalists and the media in general in a neat package. As for the first version, it contains the brochure, a summary of the project activity, information about the institutions and the Principal Investigators involved. Some of this material is also available on the project website, along with the archive of the NAP newsletters we will produce throughout the project lifespan.

When: the time

Within the COD strategy of the NAP project, we identify an indicative timing planning, in three main phases, presented in D7.2 and illustrated below:

The first phase (M1-M6) encompassed the beginning of the project and the development of the COD plan. These months have been used to build a strong and effective internal communication within the consortium, starting with the Kick-off Meeting (March 2023, Pisa) and through monthly remote meetings. In parallel, external communication has been focused on launching the NAP project, through both the social channels and the website of NAP and the institutions involved in the project. This first phase has been successfully reached, as demonstrated by the impact indicators (see Table 4 and 5).

Accordingly with the timeline, the second phase (M7- M30) is focusing on reaching the stakeholders identified in the subsection above, in order to create synergies and boost NAP COD potential. In addition, we foresee activities for facilitating the integration of STU team into the consortium. An example of activity to achieve both these objectives is the Brainstorming event, organized in October 2024 (see the Section ‘Actions already taken’ and Figure 3.)

As already stated in D7.2, the third phase (M31-M42) will be focused on identifying the best way to communicate, disseminate and promote the final results of the project (also taking into account the exploitation foreseen in D7.3 and its updated version D7.5).

It is also worth mentioning that we envisaged to apply for other European project calls such as the Open, Transition and Challenge calls of the European Innovation Council (EIC, Horizon), as an additional measure to promote the next steps in turning research results into social and economic innovation and allow the technology to further development.

Monitoring and evaluating the activities

For ensuring the effectiveness of our plan, we have identified different impact indicators for the different Communication/Outreach/Dissemination tools. Such indicators are summarized in Table 4 and Table 5, along with the numbers we are expected to reach at the end of the project activities, and those we have already achieved. The indicators already achieved with respect to what we have estimated are highlighted in bold in the last column of the tables.

Table 4 Impact indicators and their estimation for the dissemination tools, and what we have already achieved in the first year

Dissemination tools	Indicators	Indicator estimations	Achieved
Open Science publications	Number of Publications published	At least 12 publications	2
	Number of Special Issues	At least 1 special issue "Sleep: from basics to clinics"	-
Conferences* & events promoted by Scient Organizations	Number of Conferences attended	At least 19 conferences	5
	Workshop organized/attended	At least 1 Workshop	-
Brochure, posters, roll-up banners	Number of roll-up banners	1 roll-up banner	1
	Number of brochures	600 brochures	300
	Number of posters	At least 10 posters	4
Webinars/seminars and Demos	Number of seminars/webinars	At least 3 seminars/webinars	5
	Number of demos	At least 3 Demos, available on NAP YouTube account	-
Policy briefs	Number of policy briefs	At least 2 policy briefs (on sleep health and equity and 3Rs), with at least 150 downloads.	-

* Federation of EU Neuroscience Societies, SLEEP, European Sleep Research Society, MIND, national conferences like FENS, ASDAM, Radioelektronika, etc.

Table 5 Impact indicators and their estimation for the Communication and Outreach tools, and what we have already achieved in the first year

Communication Outreach tools	Impact indicators	Indicator estimation	Achieved
NAP website & social (LinkedIn, Instagram, Facebook, YouTube)	Number of views	At least 1000 views	
	Number of followers	At least 400 followers	400

	Number of social impressions	At least 800 social impressions	800
Radio, journals and TV	Number of interviews	At least 6 interviews	12
Press kits	Number of press kits distributed	At least 52 press kits	30
Newsletters Sleep pills; articles on webzines; blogs; podcasts	Number of views for each digital content	At least 50 views for each digital content	17
Lab visits, Open Doors	Number of events per year	At least 4 events/yearly	3
Café Science; Research Nights; Sleep & Brain Week	Number of participants	At least 40 participants at each event	Averagely, 100
Citizen Science experiment: Let's take a NAP...for NAP	Number of data collected	At least data for 80 people	-

Among these activities, we prefer, when possible, online solutions as a viable alternative for a cheaper, more efficient, equitable and sustainable culture.

Actions already taken

The NAP Communication, Outreach and Dissemination activities were performed at the very beginning of the project. Some examples of the actions already taken are reported below.

Other examples of activities were and will be provided on the dedicated webpage of the NAP website (<https://www.horizoneic-nap.eu/news>) and on NAP social media accounts.

Networking events – In October 2024, after the first Annual Meeting of the Consortium, we organized a scientific networking event, ‘Brainstorming’, for showcasing the first results of the project with the Pisan scientific and entrepreneur community. We choose Pisa as it is a hub for science and innovation since ever: this is reflected in the number of scientific and research institutions, as well as of SMEs and spin-offs on the territory. We organised Brainstorming with very short speeches, followed with an aperitif for letting the researchers and the stakeholders interact in a formal environment. Some pictures of the events are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 1 'Brainstorming' event (Pisa, October 2024)

Outreach events – We planned an event for the Brain Awareness Week 2025. The objective is to raise awareness about the consequences of sleep deprivation, and the importance of sleep quality for life quality, particularly focusing on the impact of sleep on brain microcircuitry. The event will consist in two parallel activities, tailored for kids (5-12 years) and adults respectively. In this way, we can engage the broader variety of ages, while ensuring activities suitable for the whole family. We do believe that involving the whole family can be a successful strategy for stimulating a change in their habits.

Dissemination events - NAP Beneficiaries are aware of the importance of disseminating the project results during national and international conferences and events promoted by Scientific Organizations, and they were committed to do it from the very beginning of the project. An example of an event for disseminating very preliminary results of the project is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 24 Marc Keller at iMNEs in Berlin

This project has received funding from the European Union's HORIZON EIC programme under grant agreement No 101099310.